

Action plan 2024–2027

1. Organisation	Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences
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1. Adherence to the core commitments of CoARA

Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences (hereon SeAMK) signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment on March 14th, 2023. We aim to ensure that the evaluation of research and researchers acknowledges diverse forms of research outputs, methodologies, and engagement, taking into account various career paths and individual circumstances while assessing the quality and impact of research. Full agreement can be accessed at: [CoARA agreement](#)

1.1 The Core Commitments of CoARA

By signing the CoARA Agreement, SeAMK adheres to the following:

1. Recognise the **diversity** of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
2. Base research assessment primarily on **qualitative evaluation** for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based **metrics**, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
4. Avoid the use of **rankings** of research organisations in research assessment.
5. Commit **resources** to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to.
6. Review and **develop** research assessment criteria, tools and processes.
7. **Raise awareness** of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
8. **Exchange** practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
9. **Communicate** progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.

10. **Evaluate** practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

1.2 Universities of Applied Science – special characteristics of research

The primary obstacles encountered in the CoARA process originate from the conventions of academic research. While the misuse of bibliometric indicators poses a significant issue in certain scientific fields, its impact on Research, Development, and Innovation (RDI) functions within University of Applied Sciences (UASs) is comparatively limited. UAS-driven RDI work is distinguished by a strong focus on development-oriented projects, applied research, and interdisciplinary collaboration. According to Finnish law, UASs hold a crucial position in the regional competence, business and well-being ecosystem, naturally guiding our efforts toward impactful outcomes. This orientation is evident in our assessment practices, recruitment procedures, and career development initiatives.

Despite the incorporation of impact and diversity in various evaluation practices, it is essential to articulate and refine our existing methods. This not only ensures transparent and equitable evaluation processes for our staff but also allows us to share our best practices with diverse research organizations and environments. In the long run, this approach has the potential to enhance the flexibility of researchers moving between different research organizations.

UASs are relatively new players in the Finnish RDI landscape. The growth of UAS-driven RDI operations underscores the necessity for more systematic and transparent evaluation criteria. The CoARA process presents an excellent opportunity for us to meticulously define our strengths and communicate them to other RDI stakeholders, authorities, and funders at both national and international levels. Additionally, it provides a platform for refining our procedures.

1.2 RDI work at Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences

SeAMK is a multidisciplinary institution of higher education and an efficient actor in education and research, development, and innovation in the region of South Ostrobothnia in West Finland. The RDI and regional operations in SeAMK have received a Quality Label for Excellence from the Finnish Education Evaluation Center (FINEEC) after a rigorous evaluation process in 2022. This shows that SeAMK has developed its RDI functions toward operation culture that emphasizes societal interaction and impact creation. The evaluation also acknowledged our long-term development work to operate in national and international networks to promote innovations in our regions.

RDI activities in SeAMK is mainly applied research and development work serving the region of South Ostrobothnia. RDI activities are guided by SeAMK strategy, the Ministry of Education and Culture's vision for higher education and research and other guiding

documents, e.g., the Southern Ostrobothnia Regional Strategy, including the Smart Specialization Strategy. Moreover, our research is closely connected to our teaching activities.

The profile areas of SeAMK's RDI are: Growth Entrepreneurship and Business Transfers, Smart Industry, Food Safety and Food Technology, Digitalization of Social and Health Sector, and Circular Economy with Sustainability. In practice the RDI work is implemented in nine research groups which are: Digital Factory, Wellbeing Technology, Growth Entrepreneurship and Business Transfers, Sustainable and Responsible Food Production, Tourism and Experience Business Development, Inclusive Society and Working Life, Food Technology and Food Safety, Health Promotion and Care, and Future Vehicle Technologies.

SeAMK has about 130 projects financed with external funding each year, and the yearly external funding is about 6.5 million euros. The key funding instruments are Structural Funds, Rural Development Fund, various ministries and, increasingly (approximately 20%) various international funding sources e.g., Horizon Europe, Erasmus+ and Interreg. We have approximately 100 full time RDI experts, and in addition to this, teachers actively participate in RDI projects.

SeAMK is committed to develop its activities according to the national Declaration for Open Science and Research and the RDI guidelines and are based on it. The aim is to promote the transparency of RDI activities by opening the operating culture, research materials and methods, publications, learning and learning materials.

Our RDI volume is constantly growing. Thus, we also need to adapt our organization, and operations to match the growing demands. In addition to the personal level challenges in researcher evaluation, we see the CoARA process as an excellent opportunity to review and further develop our organization-level RDI evaluation and reporting practices.

2 Objectives

In accordance with CoARA, SeAMK aims to evaluate and update the assessment practices on three levels: 1) Research, 2) Researchers and other persons working on research, and 3) Research Organizations.

1) Research

We must ensure that SeAMK's research assessment practices primarily rely on qualitative methodologies that are supported with responsible use of quantitative indicators. Emphasizing employee motivation to participate in RDI activities that produce substantial societal impact, maintain the highest quality standards, and foster collaboration and openness is crucial. Presently, the assessment of research within University of Applied Sciences (UASs) deviates from academic research traditions by steering clear of reliance on metrics derived from journals, publications, or analogous numerical benchmarks. Nonetheless, it remains crucial to proactively safeguard against

the potential adoption of inappropriate quantitative assessment practices in the future either.

2) Researchers and other persons working on research

On an individual level, we ensure that the merits of individual researchers and other persons involved with research are evaluated in a transparent and fair process. We will evaluate our current processes carefully and, if needed, implement novel evaluation strategies and tools that help us recognize an even larger variety of research and research-associated merits. The researcher career path (tenure track) model has been in place at SeAMK for three years, and we intend to enhance its development. We already acknowledge the varied contributions to research, including societal impact, business and university networks, level of expertise and project management, popular publications. As a component of this reform, we will however, reassess the evaluation process and, when needed, explore innovative strategies and tools for researcher assessment.

3) Research Organizations

Finland is widely acknowledged for its leadership in promoting responsible research and assessing researchers, with extensive national collaboration overseen by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (Tieteellisten seurain valtuuskunta, TSV). The CoARA agreement aligns with Finland's previously issued national recommendations, outlining a schedule for implementing reforms.

Additionally, SeAMK undergoes regular evaluations conducted by authorities and RDI funding bodies, and our funding is directly impacted by the outcomes of these assessments. We appreciate the opportunity presented by CoARA to emphasize the importance of applied research and enhance the visibility of University of Applied Sciences (UASs) as capable project partners and coordinators of applied research initiatives at the EU level.

3 Current situation and work packages of forthcoming actions

Commitment: SeAMK has signed the CoARA agreement and, thus, is committed to evaluating and developing research and research assessment practices according to CoARA principles. Moreover SeAMK has signed the following documents: *Guidelines of the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity* (Tutkimuseettisen neuvottelukunnan ohjeet) and *Declaration on Open Science and Research 2020 – 2025* (e.g., Good Practices in Researcher Evaluation - National Recommendation for Responsible Researcher Evaluation).

In the Table 1 research and researcher assessment current and forthcoming methods and processes are presented. Moreover time schedule and responsible party has been determined.

WP 1. Research evaluation and forthcoming development initiatives

Current situation		Forthcoming development initiatives	Time schedule	Responsible team
Level	A description of current state			
Whole SeAMK's RDI activities	Currently, organizational-level assessment has mainly been conducted by Karvi (Finnish Education Evaluation Centre). Naturally, regional development agencies and funders provide continuous feedback. In addition, SeAMK participates biennially in monitoring Open Science and Research.	Peer review among strategic higher education partners	2026	RDI Management Team
RDI proposal evaluation	Each project requires a preparation permit before commencing preparation. When assessing the preparation permit, suitability of the theme, realism of the funding, and expertise of the preparation team are required. Additionally, the project preparation is sparred by an external person who evaluates the project plan, especially from the perspective of funding source evaluation criteria. Finally, the project is evaluated by the RDI management group before its submission.	The evaluation criteria are specified and the sparring process is streamlined.	2024	RDI Management Team
Research proposal evaluation		SeAMK's internal research project calls are evaluated more extensively based on the RRA criteria than before (e.g. quality, openness, impact, diversity, inclusiveness, collaboration)	2025	Vice President

RDI project evaluation	Each RDI project undergoes an impact assessment upon its completion, and a so-called impact slide is produced from the project. The impact is primarily assessed from qualitative and comprehensive perspectives.	The criteria for evaluating impact slide are refined based on RRA criteria. In addition to impact slide, an impact measurement tool is developed for evaluating projects. The tool utilizes diverse criteria.	2024	RDI Management Team
Research groups	Research groups set diverse goals for their activities and evaluate their performance in the form of interim reports. Advisory Boards of Research Group are beginning their activities.	<p>The research groups conduct self-assessment systematically once a year.</p> <p>Peer mentoring among research groups is introduced.</p> <p>The criteria for goal setting and evaluation are examined from the perspective of Coara criteria (RRA).</p> <p>Advisory Boards and Senior Fellows participate to some extent in the evaluation.</p> <p>Setting criteria for the formation a new research group and dissolution of existing research. group.</p> <p>External evaluation may be implemented at some point.</p>	2025	RDI Management Team
Publications	Manuscripts submitted to publication series, SeAMK Journal, and online magazine are evaluated by both internal and external reviewers. A wide variety of publications, both scholarly and more practical, are accepted for publication.	In publication evaluation, COARA criteria are taken into account.	2025	Publication committee

WP 2. Researcher evaluation and forthcoming development initiatives

Current situation		Forthcoming development initiatives	Time schedule	Responsible team
	A description of current state			
Recruitment	Both quantitative and qualitative assessment	Narrative curriculum vitae also in use Determining the need profile for principal lecturers and lecturers. In teacher and R&D staff recruitment needs, diversity is taken into account.	2026	HR team Education and RDI Management teams
Tenure track	Since 2020, in the tenure track career path, the possibility for positions as research professor, research lecturer, RDI specialist, and principal researcher based on diverse assessment. We utilize the curriculum vitae template provided by TENK (Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity).	The evaluation criteria are being developed to be more comprehensive, taking into account the RRA criteria (more qualitative criteria). Career paths are also developed for non-PhD research and development experts as well as teachers	2024 2024-2026	SeAMK Management Team RDI Management team Education Management Team
Principal Lecturer Evaluation	Since 2017 the work results of principal lecturers are assessed every two years in relation to the set objectives (publications, RDI project preparation, RDI project implementation, international networks, supervision of theses, teaching).	The evaluation criteria are being developed to be more comprehensive, taking into account the RRA criteria (more qualitative criteria).	2025	SeAMK Management Team
Other kind of rewarding	Currently there is no other person-based rewarding.	Defining criteria (also RRA) and having comprehensive discussions (board, management team, HR, staff)	2025-2027	HR Team SeAMK Management Team

WP 3. Analysis of results and piloting new approaches

Analysis of research and researcher assessment will be conducted in order to recognize the primary deficiencies. After the assessment and subsequent analysis and selection process, a range of 2-4 challenges will be chosen. These interventions may consist of small-scale pilots or more substantial modifications to organizational-level assessment policies.

WP 4. Management and networks

Management and dissemination

The implementation of the CoARA action plan is overseen by SeAMK's management team, with the vice president as the primary responsible party. The extended management team of RDI serves as the operational working group. The education management team is a key player in developing the educational career pathway. Internal communication efforts ensure that our staff is informed about the process and comprehend the reasons behind the evolution of the evaluation framework, both within our institution and beyond. The process is showcased on SeAMK's homepage and intranet.

The Action Plan undergoes an annual review and update process. Insights and guidelines from the CoARA working groups and the national chapter will be incorporated into the Action Plan. Additionally, we ensure that the plan is responsive to the evolving needs within SeAMK's internal processes. A mid-term review will be performed at the end of 2025 and the final evaluation at the end of 2027.

External networks

SeAMK has three important stakeholders where it can learn from and share CoARA practices. SeAMK has joined as member of the **Finnish National Chapter**. We will engage actively in discussions and advocate for topics that are particularly relevant to the UAS sector. The National Chapter serves as a platform for dialogue among various research organizations, funders, and authorities to develop shared criteria for research and researcher assessment.

SeAMK actively participates in the **network of Finnish Universities of Applied Sciences**. Ongoing dialogues ensure the prompt and effective adoption of CoARA principles at a national scale. This network serves as a lasting collaborative platform, enabling the continued implementation of advancements in research assessment beyond the active working periods of the National Chapter.

Moreover SeAMK is active in Avoin TKIO-verkosto.

This document is accepted by

SeAMK Management Team 28.3.2024

Schedule

		2024	2025	2026	2027
WP 1. Research evaluation and forthcoming development initiatives					
T1.1	Whole SeAMK's RDI activities				
T1.2	RDI proposal evaluation				
T1.3	Research proposal evaluation				
T1.4	RDI project evaluation				
T1.5	Research groups				
T1.6	Publications				
WP 2. Researcher evaluation and forthcoming development initiatives					
T2.1	Recruitment				
T2.2	Tenure track				
T2.3	Principal Lecturer Evaluation				
T2.4	Other kind of rewarding				
WP 3. Analysis of results and piloting new approaches					
WP 4. Management and networks					
T4.1	Management and dissemination				
T4.2	External networks				
	the green color signifies new actions				